

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF VACCINES IN HUMAN LIFE

Kamala Rustamova

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Abstract

Unlike most drugs, whose benefit is restricted to the individual who takes the drug, prophylactic vaccines have the potential for far-reaching effects that encompass health service utilisation, general health and wellbeing, cognitive development and, ultimately, economic productivity. The impact of immunisation is measured by evaluating effects directly on the vaccinated individual, indirectly on the unvaccinated community (herd protection), the epidemiology of the pathogen (such as changing circulating serotypes or prevention of epidemic cycles), and the additional benefits arising from improved health. Aside from protection of the individual, the broader success of immunisation is dependent on achieving a level of coverage sufficient to interrupt transmission of the pathogen. When evaluating the cost-effectiveness of vaccines, all of these potential benefits need to be accounted for. In many countries where immunisation programmes have been highly successful, the control of disease has meant that the benefits of immunisation have become less obvious. Once a well-known and much-feared disease appears to have disappeared, individuals, including healthcare professionals, no longer view ongoing prevention with the same sense of urgency. Reduced coverage is inevitably associated with resurgence in disease, with outbreaks potentially leading to significant morbidity and loss of life.

Keywords: immunization, proteins, toxoid vaccines, *effective*

*Human use of preparations to prevent specific infections have been described since 1500 AD, beginning in China (Needham, 2000) where smallpox was prevented by variolation, which is the introduction of material from scabs into the skin. In 1796 in the United Kingdom, Edward Jenner observed the immunity to smallpox of milkmaids having previously had natural infection with cowpox (Jenner, 1798). He determined that inoculating small amounts of pus from the lesions of cowpox, presumably containing a virus related to vaccinia, into susceptible hosts rendered them immune to smallpox. The vaccine against smallpox was developed in 1798. The next phase of scientific developments involving the manipulation of infectious agents to extract suitable vaccine antigens took almost a century of research. Louis Pasteur's work with attenuation by oxygen or heat led to live-attenuated chicken cholera, inactivated anthrax and live-attenuated rabies vaccines at the turn of the 20th century (Pasteur, 1880, 1881, 1885). Alternative methods of attenuation using serial passage of *Mycobacterium bovis* led to the live Bacille Calmette-Guerin (BCG) (Calmette, 1927) vaccine, still in use today for the prevention of tuberculosis. Serial passage was also used in the development of yellow fever vaccines (Theiler and Smith, 1937a) which are grown in chicken embryo tissues (Theiler and Smith, 1937b). Whole cell killed bacterial vaccines were developed when methods to treat and kill bacteria through heat or chemicals were established and whole cell typhoid, cholera and pertussis vaccines resulted at the end of the 19th Century. In 1923, Alexander Glennie and Barbara Hopkins developed methods to inactivate bacterial toxins with formaldehyde, leading to the diphtheria and tetanus toxoid vaccines (Glennie and Hopkins, 1923).*

Advances in virus culture in vitro allowed viral pathogens to be studied in greater detail and attenuation methods due to cultivation in artificial conditions

led to the live oral polio, measles, rubella, mumps and varicella virus vaccines. In the 1960's at the Walter Reed Army Institute of Research, vaccines were developed using capsular polysaccharides (Gold and Artenstein, 1971; Artenstein, 1975), of encapsulated organisms including meningococci and later pneumococci (Austrian, 1989) and Haemophilus influenzae type b (Hib) (Anderson et al., 1972). To protect against multiple serotype variants of polysaccharide capsules, polyvalent vaccines were developed and later conjugated to carrier proteins to enhance their efficacy in infants in particular by recruiting T-cell mediated help to induce memory B-cells (Schneerson et al., 1980). Vaccines made solely from proteins were rare, with the exception of the toxoid vaccines, but the acellular pertussis vaccine containing five protein antigens, was developed to mitigate the unwanted effects of the whole cell vaccine (Sato and Sato, 1999).

The end of the 20th century marked a revolution in molecular biology and provided insights into microbiology and immunology allowing a greater understanding of pathogen epitopes and host responses to vaccination. Molecular genetics and genome sequencing has enabled the development of vaccines against RNA viruses possessing multiple variants of epitopes, such as the live and inactivated influenza vaccines (Maassab and DeBorde, 1985) and live rotavirus vaccines (Clark et al., 2006). DNA manipulation and excision allowed the use of surface antigen for hepatitis B viral vectors (Plotkin, 2014). The human papilloma virus (HPV) vaccine benefits from enhanced immunogenicity due to the formation of virus-like particles by the L1 antigen of each virus contained in the vaccine (Kirnbauer et al., 1992). Bacterial genome sequencing has provided in depth analysis of meningococcal antigens, to identify potential proteins forming meningococcal B vaccines (Serruto et al., 2012).

Vaccine development was tested in 2020 when a novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, emerged from China causing a severe acute respiratory illness, which subsequently spread globally. Within 5 months of the discovery of this virus (7th January 2020) (Zhu et al., 2020) and person-person transmission (Chan et al., 2020), 5,697,334 cases had been identified, with orders of magnitude likely not measured and almost no country escaped the pandemic. Owing to the previous advances in vaccinology, by 8th April 2020, there were 73 vaccine candidates under pre-clinical investigation (Thanh Le et al., 2020). Of these, six were in Phase 1 or 1/2 trials and one was in Phase 2/3 trials by 28th May 2020. The rapidity of this response demonstrated the ability to harness existing technologies including: RNA vaccine platforms (NCT04283461), DNA vaccine platforms (NCT04336410), recombinant vector vaccines (NCT04313127, NCT04324606) and adjuvants. The regulation, manufacturer and distribution of these vaccines will require expedition given the global public health need, from a period of many years to a matter of months. The efficacy and health impact of these vaccines is yet to be established, but if they are effective, then vaccines need to be made available for all global regions affected by SARS-CoV-2. The funding of this endeavor will prove challenging in a global context of national social and economic lockdown and massive government borrowing, but the justification for this provision will be through the multiple benefits to society that will need healthy citizens to rebuild economies in the decades post-COVID-19.

Establishing priorities for the development of vaccines against diseases prevalent in developing countries is complicated by large variations in the morbidity and mortality arising from such diseases, in their geographic distribution, in the extent of knowledge about relevant pathogens and host responses, in the resources and time required for vaccine development, and in anticipated vaccine efficacy and extent of use. This report presents a comprehensive method designed to help government decision makers set priorities for accelerated development of vaccines against important diseases in the developing world. The method can be used to assess new vaccine candidates or to reassess current contenders as additional information becomes available. The primary utilization of many of these vaccines would be for reducing morbidity and mortality in developing countries. Other uses would be for U.S. travelers to such countries, for military and other personnel stationed in them, and for response to the importation of these diseases (e.g., dengue fever) and their transmission in the United States.

The decision-making approach suggested uses similar kinds of information about the occurrence and importance of events that theoretically could be used in other methods of decision making. Because information is incomplete and because the method entails, in some instances, predicting the future, gaps must be filled by estimates or judgments by experts.

Providing a structural framework within which information and judgments are used and combined does

not of itself improve the quality of currently available information (although further research to generate new data might be guided by such a framework). Nor does it reduce the range of opinion likely to be expressed in predictions, judgments, or estimates (except as issues are more precisely defined).

The committee believes that the system it proposes is the most appropriate for the desired purpose and has implemented it with the best available data and estimates. The committee believes that the system would improve the decision-making process by making it more accessible to evaluation and reconstruction by other decision makers and by facilitating examination of the effect of alternative assumptions or estimates. However, some cautions and comments are needed to prevent misinterpretation of the power and precision of the method.

To identify the components on which quantitative information is desirable (though not necessarily available), the system (more than others) exposes areas of ignorance and uncertainty in which expert judgment, by necessity, must be used. The proposed approach uses equations to define the way in which information or estimates are combined (something not always specified in other approaches); this does not imply that the components or the results have the accuracy sometimes associated with formal mathematical calculations. The results are simply the consequence of combining both factual and uncertain quantities, both objective and subjective elements, that are an inescapable part of reaching conclusions about the preferred investments in new vaccines.

References

1. Dalkey, N.C. 1969. The Delphi Method: An Experimental Study of Group Opinion. Research Memorandum RM-58888-PR. Santa Monica, Calif.: The Rand Corporation.
2. Institute of Medicine. 1985. New Vaccine Development: Establishing Priorities, Volume I. Diseases of Importance in the United States. Washington, D.C.: National Academy Press. [[PubMed](#)]
3. Keeney, R.L., and H.Raiffa. 1976. Decisions with Multiple Objectives: Preferences and Value Tradeoffs. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
4. Office of Technology Assessment. 1980. The Implications of Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Medical Technology. U.S. Congress. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office.
5. Swartzman, D., editor; , R.A.Liroff, editor; , and K.G.Croke, editor. , eds. 1982. Cost-Benefit Analysis and Environmental Regulations: Politics, Ethics and Methods. Washington, D.C.: The Conservation Foundation.
6. Weinstein, M.C., and W.B. Stason. 1977. Foundations of cost-effectiveness analysis for health and medical practices. N. Engl. J. Med. 296(13):716–721. [[PubMed](#)]